

Орипов Элёржон Шавкатович
*Кўқон давлат педагогика институти
катта ўқитувчиси*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5911994>

АНЪАНАВИЙ ВА ЗАМОНАВИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАР УЙЎНЛИГИНИ ТАДҚИҚ ЭТИШДА ЭТНИК ОМИЛЛАРНИНГ АҲАМИЯТИ

Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада жамият барқарорлигини таъминлашда анъанавий ва замонавий қадриятларни уйғунлаштириши зарурати илмий - фалсафий жиҳатдан таҳлил этилган. Мақолада этник омилларнинг жамият барқарорлигига таъсири атрофлича ёритилган. Миллий тараққиётни таъминлашда этник омилларнинг аҳамияти ўрганилиб, тегишли хулоса ва тавсиялар ишлаб чиқилган.

Калит сўзлар: анъана, анъанавий қадрият, замонавий қадрият, этнос, турғунлик, яшовчанлик, ворисийлик, тадрижийлик, жамоавийлик

Орипов Элёржон Шавкатович
*Кокандский государственный педагогический институт
старший учитель*

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ЭТНИЧЕСКИХ ФАКТОРОВ В ИЗУЧЕНИИ СОЧЕТАНИЯ ТРАДИЦИОННЫХ И СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ.

АННОТАЦИЯ: В данной статье анализируется необходимость сочетания традиционных и современных ценностей в обеспечении стабильности общества с научно-философской точки зрения. В статье подробно рассматривается влияние этнических факторов на стабильность общества. Изучена роль этнических факторов в обеспечении национального развития и разработаны соответствующие выводы и рекомендации.

Ключевые слова: традиция, традиционные ценности, современные ценности, этнос, застой, жизнеспособность, наследование, эволюция, сообщество

Oripov Elyorjon Shavkatovich
*Kokand State Pedagogical Institute
higher teacher*

**THE IMPORTANCE OF ETHNIC FACTORS IN THE STUDY OF THE
COMBINATION OF TRADITIONAL AND MODERN VALUES.**

RESUME: *This article analyzes the need to combine traditional and modern values in ensuring the stability of society from a scientific and philosophical point of view. The article examines in detail the influence of ethnic factors on the stability of society. The role of ethnic factors in ensuring national development has been studied and appropriate conclusions and recommendations have been developed.*

Key words: *tradition, traditional values, modern values, ethnos, stagnation, vitality, inheritance, evolution, community*

When studying the relationship of traditions that have formed in the lifestyle of a particular ethnic unit, with the characteristics of a given ethnic community, it is advisable to define their social and spiritual being as an object of research. Because each ethnic unit in the process of its development faced a number of problems in time and space, invented thousands of different ways to solve them, enriched its social and spiritual experience with effective methods. Researcher L.A. Sugri explains: "In the language used by certain ethnic groups, in the material and spiritual culture that feeds them, specific forms of social unity that socialize the individual, specific features of the mental response to events of general importance are coded and programmed. - this information is equally important for the ethnos, as well as the role of genetic information for the organism"¹. Here the researcher correctly evaluates the importance of traditions in the socialization of the individual. He emphasizes that the traditions of ethnic communities are passed on to future generations not through the laws of nature, but through the laws of society.

The level of thinking of each ethnic unit is determined by its attitude to things and events, lifestyle and activities, formed on the basis of historical experience, ancient traditions. In general, "the way of life, traditions always shape the behavior of the peoples of each country. It normalizes his behavior, his attitude to events, he is absorbed into the blood of the nation, takes his place in a thousand and one cells"²

From the essence of the social processes of recent years, it is clear that the calmness and prudence of our President Sh.Mirziyoyev in his style of work means that our national policy is based on traditional values.

Traditional values ensure a certain development of the life and activities of an ethnic unit. In a society based on traditional values, the human mind that develops naturally forms dependence on these values. Sociologists W. Thomas and F. Znanetsky, who scientifically analyzed this process, explain it by the concept of "individual orientation towards values." They explain the emphasis on values as "a person's social orientation that regulates behavior"³. Values play an important role in the life and work of people only if they are correctly understood and understood. In studying this study, we investigated aspects relevant to our scientific topic. In our opinion, the orientation towards values reflects the totality of life experience and spiritual experience of an ethnic unit in the consciousness of

¹Сугрей.Л.А Традиционализм в контексте социально-философского анализа. Ставрополь. Автореф. док. филос. наук. 2003. стр. 16

² Иброҳимов А., Султонов Х., Жўраев Н. Ватан туйғуси. – Т.: Ўзбекистон, 1996. – Б. 330.

³ Американская социологическая мысль: Тексты. М., Изд-во МГУ, 2004.

an individual and serves to form socially significant traits in it. Thanks to traditional values, a strong, stable set of values is formed in a person's consciousness, which becomes the axis of consciousness that ensures inheritance, combining the ideals, desires, needs and interests of a person with behavior and activities ancestors. This is why traditional values are important as a factor that governs and regulates a person's inner experiences.

In the modern world, interest in traditional forms of values is growing day by day. These include national sports that connect the past and present of the people, national folklore, creative initiative, national folk medicine and pedagogy, holidays and religious rituals, national ethics and cooking. Studying these traditional values, one can penetrate into the inner world of people, reveal their unique features. Tradition is a strong chain of sacred spiritual norms that bind the past, present and future of humanity. In terms of teaching, traditions take an active part in public life through ethics, rules and management skills, housing, parenting practices, and drug treatment of patients. In our opinion, in ensuring the longevity of traditions:

- stability;
- vitality;
- inheritance;
- gradual;
- community;
- a high level of adherence to patterns of behavior;

Features such as mutual assistance and strength of support are of particular importance. Traditions work in all social systems and their activity is a necessary condition. The bad attitude of mankind towards traditions leads to a disruption in the development of the inherited society and culture. "Blind adherence to tradition generates fanaticism and inaction in public life"⁴ Traditions correctly assess how and what to inherit.

In the formation and development of traditional values, the following factors inherent in a particular ethnic unit are important: traditions, customs and rituals; degree of integration; the nature and scope of the division of labor, the desire to improve it; historical, ethnic and geographic environment; spiritual and cultural heritage in the broadest sense of the word; values, lifestyle and striving for ethnic unity. These factors not only contribute to the development of traditional values, but also nourish and strengthen them.

Traditions play an important role in the life and activities of ethnic unity: they regulate, direct, console, value, educational, aesthetic pleasures, bring them together, and provide information. In particular, Kh. Yuldashev rightly noted: "Freedom of speech and the press reveal shortcomings in society, eliminate them, prevent the deviation of power from democratic values, provide a variety of ideas, open the way for scientific and artistic creativity, awaken citizens, and develop their abilities. This is an invaluable value. is to help make it happen. Indifference to him leads to indifference among citizens and to irresponsibility and selfishness among leaders; Hypocrisy replaces sincerity"⁵

⁴ Социология” А. А. Радугин, К. А. Радугин, Москва, 2003 г. Издательство “Центр”. Стр. 49.

⁵ <https://khyuldoshev.wordpress.com/2015/04/30/qadriyatlar-tuqnashuvi/>. Date of application 24.03.2021

The harmonious functioning of these functions of traditions forms an effective mechanism for managing ethnic unity and contributes to the development of "exemplary behavior" in ethnic consciousness. In particular, at a time when our people are moving from a strong state to a strong civil society, thanks to the structural and functional analysis of these traditions, first of all, it becomes possible to apply them in practice.

REFERENCES:

1. Сугрей Л. А. Традиционализм в контексте социально-философского анализа. Ставрополь. Автореф. док. филос. наук. 2003. стр. 16
2. Иброхимов А., Султонов Х., Жўраев Н. Ватан туйғуси. – Т.: Ўзбекистон, 1996. – Б. 330.
3. Американская социологическая мысль: Тексты. М., Изд-во МГУ, 2004.
4. Социология” А. А. Радугин, К. А. Радугин, Москва, 2003 г. Издательство “Центр”. Стр. 49.